

Renewable Energy and Climate Change in Developing Countries: Challenges and Adaptation

Esther Tammy Andoya^{1*}

¹International Relations and Diplomacy, Shanghai University

Accepted June 18,2021
Published June 25,2021

*Corresponding Author:
Esther Tammy Andoya,

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5032315>

Pages : 139-154

Funding: -

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):
Andoya Esther T., (2021).
Renewable Energy and Climate
Change in Developing Countries:
Challenges and Adaptation.
*North American Academic
Research*, 4(6), 139-154. doi:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5032315>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

There is a recognized, increasing need for developing countries to sustain the growing demand for energy which has given rise to multiple policy development needs and energy resource scaling. This study also highlights the challenges of transitioning to renewable energy based electrical structures and implementation policy strategy for energy demanding developing countries exploring the options of their future.

In examining the intersection of climate policy and national development policy, this paper investigates the influence and implications of national and local politics when developing complex national energy strategies, and which strongly influences the prospects of realizing goals of international climate change policy with renewable energy development for developing countries.

Keywords: CLIMATE CHANGE, RENEWABLE ENERGY, DEVELOPING COUNTRIES, ENERGY EFFICIENT, NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT, POWER GRID

Introduction

Renewable sources like solar photovoltaic (PV), wind, hydroelectric, and geothermal, are becoming attractive options because of their low carbon impact, indefinite supply, price stability and economic benefits. For emerging economies to have efficient energy distribution, climate policy strategy must be integrated into development structural objectives. (1)

However, renewable energy sources have challenges as well, like initial development costs, maintenance costs, an intermittent energy supply, and other problems to supply a stable, base load of electricity on demand.(2) Research has shown that energy accessibility and economic progress of any developing country are intricately linked.(3)

Over the past ten years, many developing countries have attempted to achieve sustainable development goal (SDG) and meet global indicators. Even though many these countries have taking considerable steps towards poverty alleviation such as Nigeria, South Africa, Brazil, etc. there still remain the core challenge of policy implementation: poverty. For example, in Bangladesh more than 63 million people live below the poverty line with the constant threat of sudden occurring natural and man-made disasters and with an

increasingly competitive international trade environment impeded by higher growth rates.(4) Renewable energy technologies (RET) hold important roles in future energy use and economic prosperity as well as eventually lead to a faster transition towards a developed society.(5) Still, it remains unclear to many observers whether renewable energy implementations in accord with global climate policy can satisfy national strategic energy security and development needs.(6)

While this study is predominantly qualitative methodology, some of the literature reviewed for this research, used both qualitative and quantitative data analysis hence, solid secondary data is analyzed to determine the potential for renewable energy capacity and international policy in the national development of developing countries, while considering the differences in their geographic and geologic features.(7) This study highlights a collision strategy for global climate policy and national energy development strategy for electricity energy demanding developing countries to meet the international objectives and national demand.

Methods and Framework

Inter-linkages between Climate change and Renewable energy for Sustainable development

Although Climate change does not yet feature prominently within the environmental or economic policy agendas of most developing countries, evidence shows according to research that some of the most unfavorable impacts of climate change will be in developing countries where populations are most vulnerable and least likely to easily adapt to climate change.(8) In some developing countries, interactions between global climate change policies and their national policy agenda for sustainable development does exist especially for renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable land-use policies.(9) It is important for policy makers and interest groups to consider the inclusion of global climate policy in national agenda in other to address global greenhouse gas emissions and improve renewable energy implementation policies.

The impacts of such policies on the distribution of energy to on grid and off grid communities are an important determinant of the feasibility of the potentials in establishing climate change policy infused national development plan. An approach of constructivism that is likely to achieve actual change in alignment with international climate change goals will promote the selection of renewable energy sources when either additional power sources are added or to replacement energy sources as the existing sources may fail to meet the growing demand within developing companies. Figure 1., is a graphical metric framework which reflects effective tracking of the inter-linkage relationships between the Sustainable Development Indicators (SDIs).(10)

Figure 1: A bottom-up approach to analyzing interactions across SDGs.

Therefore, according to Noreen Beg,⁽⁸⁾ the recognition of how climate change is likely to influence other development priorities may be a first step toward building cost-effective strategies and integrated, institutional capacity in developing countries to respond to renewable energy implementation and climate change mitigation.

Climate change (SDG 13.1) has been identified as one of the greatest challenges by all the nations, government, business, and citizens of the globe. ⁽¹¹⁾ The threats of climate change on our planet requires that renewable energy (SDG 7.1) contributing to total energy generation and consumption (SDG 7.b) should be significantly expanded as a matter of necessity. The sustainable development goals cannot be appropriately addressed without mentioning the “2030 Agenda” for Sustainable Development and in general, this seeks to improve health and education, reduce inequality, and spur economic growth, all while tackling climate change and working to preserve our oceans and forests.⁽¹²⁾ For example, India’s energy development program has been put under strenuous pressure with the increasing demand and supply gap and the predominance of fossil fuels in the energy mix, gives large negative environmental externalities caused by electricity generation.⁽¹³⁾

The report written by the United Nations on the interconnections read in Box 1,⁽¹¹⁾ illustrates the positively reinforcing linkages between the SDG 7 and the other which applies the need for policy implementation for developing countries to embrace sustainable development when addressing economic development on a national or regional level.

Box 1 illustrates linkages between the SDGs

Access to energy (target 7.1) also implies an increase of safety and security, contributing to reducing the incidence of violence (target 16.1) to women and inequalities (target 10.2) between sexes (women being able to walk home after work in the dark). Equally important, energy use efficiency (target 7.3) would decouple economic growth (target 8.4) with a

significant impact on the environment (target 13.1) and at the same time would improve economic productivity (target 8.2).

Economic diversification is a key component of sustainable development as it assists countries in reducing poverty (target 1.1) and generates employment (target 8.5) in the long run. The increase in the use of renewable energy (target 7.2) is critical in strengthening resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards (target 13.1) and contributes to reducing contamination of hazardous chemicals in air, water, and land (target 12.4), with significant impact on reducing the number of deaths and illness due to pollution (target 3.9).

Investments in technological innovation towards SDG 7 would stimulate innovations for water efficiency in water-pumping and irrigation systems (target 6.4) and would stimulate creation of new jobs (target 8.5), decarbonize the transport sector allowing better air quality in cities (target 11.2), ensure sustainable production and consumption patterns (target 12.a) and reduce fuel consumption with environmental benefits (targets 12.c and 13.2).

There is an increasing role for women in promulgating clean energy infrastructure development (targets 5.a and 5.b), in rural areas in the Asia-Pacific region, which has contributed to new opportunities for economic growth (SDG 8) and greenhouse gas emissions reduction (target 13.1)

Universal access to affordable, reliable, and modern energy services (target 7.1) is crucial for vulnerable people to meet diverse basic services, such as access to drinking water and sanitation (target 6.1), access to health care (targets 3.7 and 3.8), access to education (target 4.1), access to information (target 9.c) and access to adequate and safe housing (target 11.1) with important contribution to reducing poverty in all its dimensions (target 1.2).

It is essential to develop and promote alternative energy sources that can lead to the sustainability of energy.(14)

The Importance of Renewable Energy for Developing countries

Renewable energy (RE) is known to be sources of vast, clean, and increasingly competitive energy and in modern times, differs from non-renewable energy sources such as fossil fuels principally in its diversity and potential for use anywhere on the planet. Renewable energy technology (RET) for electricity has become synonymous with CO₂ emissions reduction and as such an alternative and sustained energy source, that is, renewable energy resources, (RES) their potential and achievements is therefore, an important resource for climate change mitigation.(15) According to the IEA, world electricity demand will have increased by 70% by

2040 its share of final energy use rising from 18 to 24% during the same period driven mainly by the emerging economies of India, China, Africa, the Middle East and South-East Asia.(16) Fossil fuels such as oil, coal, and natural gas on the contrary are available in finite quantities only and as extractions are ongoing, it is presumed that these resources will run out sooner or later even though they produce in natural processes, fossil fuels do not replenish as quickly as humans use them. Although the world still heavily relies on fossil fuels and continuously subsidizing fossil fuels, the pollution and climate damaging GHG health endangering particles released, has reached record levels. In the IEA report an increase in RE demand for clean energy is growing exponentially as represented in their annual report where nearly half of all new electricity generation capacity installed in 2014, constituted the second biggest source of electricity worldwide, behind coal.(17)

RE resources are essentially infinite and, what is even more important, is that RE sources cause little climate or environmental damage in contrast to fossil fuels.(18) Investors of renewable energy seek short-term profitable opportunities in financial applications but are often not willing to face the large up-front costs, long payback periods and significant risks associated with investments in renewables, energy efficiency and afforestation projects that may mitigate GHG.(19) Moreover, 80% of private foreign investments are focused in 12 rapidly developing countries, meanwhile, OECD aid as a share of GDP has fallen significantly in the last decade.(8) Renewable energy investments can produce significant benefits, including lower fuel and electricity costs, increased grid reliability, better air quality and public health, and more job opportunities in developing economies.(20)

Climate change as threat to Energy Security to Developing countries

Africa

Climate change is becoming one of the most challenging issues threatening the sustainable development in Africa.(21) One of the most vulnerable continents to climate change and climate variability, a situation aggravated by the interaction of ‘multiple stresses’, occurring at various levels with low adaptive capacity. Africa’s Major economic vulnerability is its current climate sensitivity with huge economic impacts, it is aggravated by existing developmental challenges such as poverty, complex governance, and institutional dimensions; limited access to capital, including markets, infrastructure, and technology.(22) Climate variability and change, coupled with human-induced changes, may also affect ecosystems e.g., mangroves and coral reefs, with additional consequences for fisheries and tourism.(2) The projection that sea-level rise could increase flooding, particularly on the coasts of eastern Africa, will have implications for health. Sea-level rise will probably increase the high socio-economic and physical vulnerability of coastal cities.

The cost of adaptation to sea-level rise could amount to at least 5-10% of gross domestic product.(23) For example, in Nigeria, as of 2009, over 11 oil companies in the Niger Delta produced 2.7 million barrels of crude oil each day, flaring about 17 billion cubic meters of associated gas and spewing 2 700 tons of particulates, 160 tons of Sulphur oxides, 5400 tons of carbon monoxide, and 12 and 3.5 million tons of methane and carbon

dioxide, respectively. It is evident that the present patterns of fossil fuel use and the related emission of greenhouse gases are not sustainable.(17)

As studies through the region appear to have shown that countries with abundant resources of fossil fuel exert negative impacts on the environment with little benefits to the society. It is, therefore, no wonder the volatility of the oil prices and impacts of global climate change have compelled many African countries to explore the potentials of renewable energy technology (RET) for sustainable development. It also encourages the use of financial and technical cooperation by countries to adopt more climate-friendly policies and technologies such as RET. The adoption and deployment of RET have, however, been advocated as capable of mitigating the threats of climate change. However, energy efficiency, demand management, optimal generation planning, improved grid operation and increased electricity trade across African countries have also been proposed as options that could complement RETs in ensuring energy security for the region.(20)

In the same light, many African energy analysts have come to terms with the fact that RET provides a sustainable alternative to most oil-exporting and non-oil-exporting nations because of the abundance of unexploited renewable energy resources such as biomass, hydropower, solar, geothermal and wind. Another important factor is the increase in rate of electricity consumption in Africa. A study has revealed that Africa's final electricity consumption is expected to double between 2007 and 2030 from 505 to 1012 TW/h. It is important to note here, that Climate change is only one of many securities, environmental and developmental challenges facing Africa and its impacts will be magnified or moderated by underlying conditions of governance, poverty, and resource management, as well as the nature of climate change impacts at local and regional levels. Adaptation policies and programs, if implemented quickly and at multiple scales, could help avert climate change considering external interests such as existing social, political, and economic tensions and other environmental stress in other to avoid triggers for conflict.(5) In other words, the intensity behind renewable energy lies in its ability to be renewed, and the sustainability of its harvesting, conversion and usage and economic value. In the awakening of the search for functional and sustainable economies, a few developing countries have put policies in place for the deployment of RET, although this excludes how effectively they have operated.

To illustrate, the policy instrument introduced in South Africa to support of RET was the Renewable Energy Feed-In Tariff (REFIT), yet the share of renewable energy for electricity generation is very insignificant while in the case Egypt, the country has one of the largest wind farms in Africa.(24) The Zafarana wind farm has a total number of 222 turbines providing an installed capacity of 140 MW and it is planned to expand this to 600 MW. After the adoption of RET in any developing country, it is imperative that the technical capability to adapt the technology either by imitation or reverse engineering and policy be made; This is could also be better carried out through government-funded R&D at the earlier stage before transferring it to the private sector, an example of this could be found in Brazil where the Centro de Tecnologia Canavieira (Cane

Technology Centre), an R&D facility funded largely by the sugarcane industry, has decoded the genome of sugarcane, thereby developing varieties that are more resistant to drought and pests.(22)

Asia and the Pacific

Energy demand is projected to almost double as well in the Asia and Pacific region by 2030 and there is the urgent need for innovative ways to generate power in a socially, economically, and environmentally sustainable manner for some of these developing nations.(25) Like in Africa and Latin America, compounding the problem is widespread energy poverty across Asia, with almost a billion people still without access to electricity.(26) Energy efficiency is emerging as one of the key options that can help nations in Asia and the Pacific meet the region's growing energy needs in a clean and effective way. Asia-Pacific is also one of the most vulnerable regions to climate change and its impacts are projected to become more intense in the future. Like every other region in the world, it also accounts for nearly half of global GHG emissions. According to IRENA (The International Renewable Energy Agency), the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) recognizing the rising demand for energy aims to rely more on renewables to support a sustainable, secure, and prosperous future. (27) Therefore, the region has set out to make 23% of its primary energy renewable by 2025, even as under current policies only accounts for a reaching 17% of renewables compared to 9.4% in 2014. A good example for the region is Singapore and the Philippines, sustainable development is the main objective of the Philippines and Singapore and, as well as all the Asia – and Pacific countries, even though achieving this objective will demand different approaches and policy. (26) This is due to the obvious reason of levels of development, availability and affordability of renewable energy technologies, geographical and geological differences, and policy implementation.

In Singapore, a region where piped and liquefied natural gas produces the largest share of its electricity, the government announced a US\$36 million Low-Carbon Energy Research Funding Initiative at the Singapore International Energy Week of 2020, in a bid to accelerate its transition towards a cleaner and more sustainable future". Simultaneously, both Japan and South Korea also set 2050 as their target to be carbon neutral. Studies shown that, in the Asia Pacific region, energy poverty is the highest in the sub-regions of South Asia, Southeast Asia and in the Pacific Island Countries. According to the UNEP Most people without energy access are in areas that face the most difficult geographic challenges that is, rural, remote and islands. Developing countries in the Asia-Pacific region with the largest electricity access deficit are India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Indonesia, and Myanmar while, regions with high proportion of the population without energy access located in the Oceania region includes but not limited to Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands and Vanuatu. It is stressed that environmental sustainability was an integral part of a resilient economy, and that this would be an opportunity for the green sector to develop into a growth industry hence, Asia - Pacific pledge net zero pledge 2050 and enhanced international cooperation to promote innovative technological solutions; develop and scale up sustainable business models and increase financing and investment as a means to realize the goals set under the 2030 Agenda, in Sustainable Development Goal 7 on energy. (28) The UN Environment Program fosters and

supports countries in confronting the dual challenge of adapting to a changing climate at the same time as addressing greenhouse gas emissions using renewable energy and clean technology.(29) According to environmental think tank German watch, the Asia-Pacific regions are home to five of the ten countries most impacted by the effects of climate change in 2018, these countries are Japan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, India, and Fiji. This has become a wake-up call and an opportunity for the region to hasten the switch to cleaner energy sources. For developing countries of Asia - Pacific, climate change and renewable energy development should center around:

- Improving policies and best practices
- Harnessing technology and assessing technological needs for utilization and transfer.
- Incorporating climate change and renewable energy planning and policy into national and sectoral policies for implementation
- Accelerating readiness for local investment.(28)

Increasing the efficiency of energy use and supply yields lower costs and increases availability of energy. It also produces large environmental and economic benefits, eases growth in fossil fuel demand and on upward pressure on energy prices, improves energy security and reduces greenhouse gas emissions by deploying technical advances that have amplified the viability of new renewable sources of energy as well as the option for off-grid, community-based electricity supply.(30)

Latin America

Central America is a region with rapidly increasing energy needs. Several protests have rattled various governments across Latin America and the Caribbean in recent months and yet some of these were influence of long term challenges like climate change as people demand better policy choices and lower levels of inequality.(31) Polls consistently show that people fear climate change far more than do people in other regions. Home to over 40 million people and with an economy growing more than a 3 per cent per year, climate change has become a major drive force and influences other sustainable goals while having a dramatic effect on Latin America and the Caribbean. Most people in the region view climate change as a major peril and Costa Rica, Chile and 21 other regional countries have announced plans to become “net-zero” emitters by 2050.(32) The natural conditions and climate unpredictability of the region makes it vulnerable to natural disasters, and in the region of approximately 7 million people there still is limited or no access to basic electricity. It is estimated that regional governments will spend about \$77 billion between now and 2030 to meet their climate change goals and public investment covers only about a quarter of that while a tiny share could come from multilateral banks. The need for companies to also invest in more green projects to fulfill their own environmental, social and governance (ESG) goals. Unfortunately, investors will only invest massively in environmentally friendly public projects if it is easy to operate and if they are confident their money will truly make a difference or give returns. Since Investors need guarantees that their cash will fund environmentally sustainable projects, and not

simply be used to build bridges or fund budget gaps, institutions like the Inter-American Development Bank, French Development Agency could come in to help developing Latin America countries curb emissions and promote green-friendly investment regulations.(33) According to Climate Bonds Initiative, Latin American and Caribbean countries issued close to \$5 billion in green bonds, bringing the region's overall historic total to \$13.6 billion, in 2019 and more than 300 investors showed interest in buying Chilean green bonds. Now, those bonds are helping Chile invest in things like green buildings and electric buses. These green bonds are finally becoming a mainstream investment option in Latin America hence, they account for just 2% of the global green bond market and to truly to combat climate change through renewable energy, it is essential for developing countries of Latin America to make it even easier, and more attractive, for investors to aid these countries go green.(34)

In other to help tackle Central and Latin America's growing energy demand, the eventual reduction of the region's reliance on fossil energy sources and ultimately diversifying its energy mix, and the implementation of identified renewable energy recommendations and policy is a feasible and sustainable solution.(35) According to the Guardian, a series of meetings held on 20th and 21st of June 2017, in Panama City, brought national and regional stakeholders together to discuss the methodologies used in the Central American Clean Energy Corridor (CECCA) and to work on validating the preliminary findings of IRENA's Renewables Readiness Assessment (RRA) of Panama and together, CECCA and RRA Panama support a cost-effective integration of larger shares of renewable energy in the region.(34)

Panama's Secretary of Energy Mr. Víctor Carlos Urrutia, said, "Although, Panama has developed nearly 400 megawatts of renewable energy capacity in the last 3 years, we still need more support to reach our 70 per cent renewable energy target by 2050". Over the last 12 years the Latin American region's power demand grown by 65 per cent, and it was estimated that 7 gigawatts (GW) of new electric generation capacity will be needed by the end of 2020. To help aid this need, Central America boasts massive renewable energy potential in hydropower, biomass, geothermal, wind and solar energy sources and renewable energy deployment through:

- a). A regulatory project assessing investment incentives for wind and solar PV plants in Panama, with the aim to promote improvements through amended power purchase agreements.
- b). A project focusing on the flexibility of the national grid and on supporting the lack of renewable energy training.(34)

By doing this, Latin American developing countries could aim to ensure buy-in from national entities, while supporting the implementation of the regulatory and technical component as well as internal or private investors into green projects.

Discussion: Implementation and Strategy

The challenge of developing countries alike is insufficient after analyzing data on poverty rates and electricity, Gollwitzer concludes that electricity is a precondition to development, but will not guarantee development. In other words, without electricity there is no ‘development’, and the presence of electricity is not what causes development; it is just an essential ingredient to development; therefore, electricity is key to the actual ‘development’ of developing countries.(36) It is widely accepted that renewable energy is the best form of electrical power to meet global climate change goals. Adapting global climate change policy into the national development framework to expand electrification with renewable energy is a solid plan to unify both development and climate change policy.

Rural electrification in developing countries can be achieved through renewable grid-extensions, mini-grids, or stand-alone power systems.(37) Unfortunately, many utilities are failing to provide reliable services and may be poorly managed or financially inept with limited options to expand distribution networks, the grid. Figure 2., shows an ideal integration for policy implementation.(38)

Figure 2 Relationships between stakeholders

Rural electrification

There is increasing interest in electrification solutions in which Community Renewable Energy (CRE) models can play a role in providing access to modern energy services in rural communities including the furthest groups without expanding the grid. Moreover, policy uncertainty regarding grid extension, poor access to credit and absence of formal financial institutions at the local level discourages private entrepreneurs to venture into the sector.(39) In an off-grid sector, reinforcing the regulatory environment is important and acts as a precondition for creating an enabling environment that attracts private investment.(33) Unlike the full on-grid based systems,

a stand-alone system may consist of a few components all coming to working together to create, deliver or store energy for the electric demand.(40) This form of generation provides energy at the point of consumption such as a single building in an off-grid location, this solution often consists of diesel generators, or battery based renewable energy systems such as solar or wind, or even a combination to create a hybrid system (e.g., solar-diesel hybrid system). It is usually a battery-based system is best preference as it allows for the storage of energy for consumption as required and as per demand because these systems often cannot offer the most economical solution for rural electrification.(36)

Pico systems and Mini grids (or micro-grids)

These two other off-grid electrification approaches have increased in the last years, a Pico System is a small power system typically offering an electrical output no greater than a couple of 100Watts. Normally these systems present the following features a). portable b). to be used with efficient lights c). a battery is provided within the package to be used when the energy source is not available d). often incorporates small ICT, i.e., mobile phones, appliances charging point.(35) Pico Systems are often associated to Solar PV Pico systems (the so-called SPS), due to photovoltaic being a suitable technology for this approach, nonetheless other technologies like small wind generators or small diesel generators could, theoretically, play the same role.

Mini grids are said to take up a unique part of the energy ecosystem because they are larger than a single-family home system, but smaller than regional or national grids. A Mini grid is a non-centralized energy generation and distribution power facility that serves a livelihood/town, industry, or other type of client typically out of the main national grid reach with electricity.(36) Electricity can be generated from different sources i.e., solar energy, diesel generators, wind, biogas, biomass, and biofuels, although a combination of 2 resource has become more adopted in recent times, to increase the energy mix and power dispatch-ability of any given area. Mini grids may be too expensive to be built without significant resources and planning but are also deemed excessively an unproven approach to be a formal part of national grid operators' built-In strategy.(40)

Figure 3 Adaptation from PVPS

Conclusion

In the bid to extend rural electrification as suggested by this research, the Governments of developing regions may need to consider mandating mini grids as part of formal energy planning processes and policy planning. As mini grid-based electrification involves a natural monopoly component (e.g., distribution network), some form of control is required to ensure investor and consumer protection, reporting of information and incidents, and monitoring of service quality.(31,33) This will in-turn help boost investment and support these systems with financial resources and incentives where required. National energy policy should consider incorporating and promote mini grid development for rural development, energy policy or rural electrification policy and strategy. Micro grids and stand-alone systems are often less expensive to develop and are more adaptable than major grid extensions.(41)

For example, where there is low population density and electricity demand, or where there is a difficult terrain, or the region is prone to severe weather events; or some social or political conflicts exists between those controlling the grid and the persons who are of, off the grid. Some research has estimated that the implementation of micro-grids and stand- alone systems to serve off-grid communities can supply more than 50% of the additional technical capacity needed to reach universal energy access.(40) Furthermore, from studying academic literatures, it is realized that the adoption of RET in any given isolated rural community can create positive consequential outcomes and significant socio-economic production.(15) Also, as energy storage is most of the time incorporated to cover the base load at night and Mini grids are meant to have the technical capabilities to be connected to the national grid and to expand for future development. Transitioning to an energy system based renewable technologies will give rise to constructive economic outcomes on the global economy and on development. The sustainability of isolated systems using RE depends largely on regulations

and stimulation measures. Extensive research, touches on the delicate point on which RE resources could complement each other, such that in a location with enough average wind speed and a suitable area for wind turbines, wind driven storage system is a good combination with a hydro power plant/grid and if it seems profitable to use wind turbines to produce power for pumps to pump water to an upper reservoir, and to make it reusable for hydro power plants, the next step would be to design such a system and implement it.(42) Interestingly, when RE systems are owned, operated, or maintained by a community organization, either completely or partially, communities can potentially overcome some of the problems associated with other electrification models.(38) This encourages community groups to develop interest in the utilities and investment interests, embracing the social idea of integration and accepting RE technologies, and develop local maintenance capabilities and education. Therefore, RE for rural electrification can be a driver for climate change policy inspired national development and energy security while pursuing sustainability.

References

1. Tanner T, Horn-Phathanothai L. Climate change and development. *Clim Chang Dev*. 2014;1–368.
2. Muok BO, Makokha W, Plait D. Solar PV for Enhancing Electricity Access in Kenya : What Policies are Required? *Policy Br*. 2015;(July):8.
3. Ellabban O, Abu-Rub H, Blaabjerg F. Current status, future prospects and their enabling technology. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev*. 2014;39:748–764.
4. Sanni M, Egbetokun AA, Jesuleye OA, Siyanbola WO. Clean technologies as mitigating strategies against the potential impacts of climate change in 21st century Nigeria. :1–12.
5. Sanni M, Oladipo OG, Ogundari IO, Aladesanmi OT. Adopting latecomers’ strategies for the development of renewable energy technology in Africa. *African J Sci Technol Innov Dev* [Internet]. 2014 Jul 4;6(4):253–63. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/20421338.2014.924265>
6. Tanner T, Allouche J. Towards a New Political Economy of Climate Change and Development. *IDS Bull*. 2011;42(3):1–14.
7. Vandaele N, Porter W. Renewable Energy in Developing and Developed Nations: Outlook to 2040. *J Undergrad Res*. 2015;15(3):1.
8. Beg N, Morlot JC, Davidson O, Afrane-Okesse Y, Tyani L, Denton F, et al. Linkages between climate change and sustainable development. *Clim Policy*. 2002;2(2–3):129–44.
9. Kameyama Y. The future climate regime: a regional comparison of proposals. *Int Environ Agreements*. 2004;4(4):307–26.
10. Karnib A. A Quantitative Nexus Approach to Analyze the Interlinkages across the Sustainable Development Goals. *J Sustain Dev*. 2017;10(5):173.
11. Nations U. Sdginterlinkages [Internet]. *SDG Interlinkages Analysis & Visualisation Tool,SDG-Interlinkages*. 2020 [cited 2020 Oct 1]. Available from: <https://sdginterlinkages.iges.jp/>.
12. Morton S, Pencheon D, Squires N. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and their implementation.

- Br Med Bull. 2017;124(1):81–90.
13. Parikh JK, Parikh K. Climate Change: India's perceptions, positions, policies and possibilities. *Development*. 2002;30.
 14. Borowy I. Sustainable Development in Brundtland and Beyond: How (Not) to Reconcile Material Wealth, Environmental Limits and Just Distribution. 2017;(March):91–108.
 15. Petrović-Randelović M, Kocić N, Stojanović-Randelović B. The importance of renewable energy sources for sustainable development. *Econ Sustain Dev*. 2020;4(2):15–24.
 16. Renewable Energy World. Why is Renewable Energy Important. 2020. Available from: <https://www.renewableenergyworld.com/why-is-renewable-energy-important>
 17. IEA. World Energy Outlook. IEA. 2019 [cited 2020 Feb 14]. Available from: <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2014>.
 18. CRS. 2020 Green-e. CRS. 2019 [cited 2020 Dec 19]. Available from: <https://resource-solutions.org/g2020/>
 19. REN21. Why is Renewable Energy Important. 2020. Available from: <https://www.ren21.net/why-is-renewable-energy-important/>
 20. Aznar A, Logan J, Gagne D, Chen E. Advancing Energy Efficiency in Developing Countries: Lessons Learned from Low-Income Residential Experiences in Industrialized Countries. 2019;(April).
 21. BROWN OLI, HAMMILL A, MCLEMAN R. Climate change as the 'new' security threat: implications for Africa. *Int Aff* [Internet]. 2007 Nov 1;83(6):1141–54. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2346.2007.00678.x>
 22. Jaiyesimi R. The Challenge of Implementing the Sustainable Development Goals in Africa. *African J Reprod Heal / La Rev Africaine la Santé Reprod* [Internet]. 2016 Jun 22;20(3):13–8. Available from: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26357106>
 23. Below T, Artner A, Siebert R, Seiber S. Micro-level Practices to Adapt to Climate Change for African Small-scale Farmers: a review of selected literature. *IFPRI Discuss Pap*. 2010;0953(February):28.
 24. Boamong R, Phillips MA. Renewable energy incentives in Kenya: Feed-in-tariffs and Rural Expansion. 2016;
 25. Jr MG. a Review of Strategy for the Estimation of. 2002;17(30):583–98.
 26. Xiangchengzhen M, Yilmaz S. Renewable energy cooperation in Northeast Asia: Incentives, mechanisms and challenges. *Energy Strateg Rev* [Internet]. 2020;29:100468. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211467X20300225>
 27. Bataille C, Waisman H, Briand Y, Svensson J, Vogt-Schilb A, Jaramillo M, et al. Net-zero deep decarbonization pathways in Latin America: Challenges and opportunities. *Energy Strateg Rev*. 2020;30.
 28. UNESCAP. Low carbon green growth roadmap for Asia and the Pacific: turning resource constraints and the climate crisis into economic growth opportunities [Internet]. Bangkok, Thailand: United

- Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia; 2012. 220 p. Available from: <http://www.greengrowth-elearning.org/pdf/MrChung-GreenGrowth.pdf>
29. Li H, Zhao X, Yu Y, Wu T, Qi Y. China's numerical management system for reducing national energy intensity. *Energy Policy* [Internet]. 2016;94:64–76. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421516301434>
 30. UNESCAP. Low carbon green growth roadmap for Asia and the Pacific: turning resource constraints and the climate crisis into economic growth opportunities. In 2012. p. 220. Available from: <http://www.greengrowth-elearning.org/pdf/MrChung-GreenGrowth.pdf> <http://www.unescap.org/esd/publications/environment/lcgg-roadmap/Roadmap-FINAL-rev.pdf> <http://www.unescap.org/sites/default/files/Full-report.pdf>
 31. Barbosa L de SNS, Bogdanov D, Vainikka P, Breyer C. Hydro, wind and solar power as a base for a 100% renewable energy supply for South and Central America. *PLoS One* [Internet]. 2017 Mar 22;12(3):e0173820. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0173820>
 32. Inter-American Development Bank, DDPLAC. NET-ZERO EMISSIONS: Lessons from Latin America and. Inter-American Dev Bank, Washington, DC. 2019;56.
 33. Mandelli S, Barbieri J, Mereu R, Colombo E. Off-grid systems for rural electrification in developing countries: Definitions, classification and a comprehensive literature review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev.* 2016;58:1621–46. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032115017219>
 34. Madriz-Vargas R, Bruce A, Watt M. The future of Community Renewable Energy for electricity access in rural Central America. *Energy Res Soc Sci* [Internet]. 2018;35:118–31. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214629617303432>
 35. Feron S. Sustainability of off-grid photovoltaic systems for rural electrification in developing countries: A review. *Sustain.* 2016;8(12):1–26.
 36. Ministry of Energy and Petroleum, Sustainable Energy for All. Kenya Action Agenda. 2016;(January):113. Available from: http://www.se4all.org/sites/default/files/Kenya_AA_EN_Released.pdf
 37. Showers KB. ELECTRIFYING AFRICA: AN ENVIRONMENTAL HISTORY WITH POLICY IMPLICATIONS. *Geogr Ann Ser B* [Internet]. 2011 Jun 22;93(3):193–221. Available from: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41315208>
 38. Gollwitzer L. All Together Now: Institutional Innovation for Pro-Poor Electricity Access in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Univ Sussex* [Internet]. 2017; Available from: <http://sro.sussex.ac.uk/67333/1/Gollwitzer%20Lorenz.pdf>
 39. Palit D, Sarangi GK. Renewable energy based mini-grids for enhancing electricity access: Experiences and lessons from India. *Proc 2014 Int Conf Util Exhib Green Energy Sustain Dev ICUE 2014.* 2014;(March):19–21.

40. Bhattacharyya SC, Palit D. Mini-grid based off-grid electrification to enhance electricity access in developing countries: What policies may be required? *Energy Policy* [Internet]. 2016;94:166–78. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.04.010>
41. Yadoo A, Cruickshank H. The role for low carbon electrification technologies in poverty reduction and climate change strategies: A focus on renewable energy mini-grids with case studies in Nepal, Peru and Kenya. *Energy Policy* [Internet]. 2012;42:591–602. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421511010354>
42. Burton I, Huq S, Lim B, Pilifosova O, Schipper EL. From impacts assessment to adaptation priorities: the shaping of adaptation policy. *Clim Policy* [Internet]. 2002;2(2):145–59. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1469306202000384>

Abbreviations

GHG	Greenhouse gas
IEA	International Energy Agency
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
PV	Photo-voltaic
RE	Renewable Energy
RET	Renewable Energy Technology

Tammy E. Andoya is a distinguished graduate student of International Relations and Diplomacy from Shanghai University.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

